

IIFC 2023 BEST THESIS AWARD

ABSTRACTS

HYBRID GLULAM-FRP BEAM WITH IMPROVED FIRE PERFORMANCE

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FIRE BEHAVIOUR OF CONCRETE STRUCTURES REINFORCED WITH GFRP BARS

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**FRACTURE BEHAVIOUR OF PULTRUDED GFRP PROFILES: APPLICATION TO WEB-
CRIPPLING PHENOMENA**

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**LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT AND CO-PROCESSING OF WASTE FROM DECOMMISSIONED
IRISH WIND TURBINE BLADES**

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ABSTRACT

Title:

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The use of timber as a load-bearing structural material in the built environment has traditionally been perceived as not being appropriate for applications where fire safety could be a ‘problem’ – particularly for mid- or high-rise structures. In contrast with concrete or steel, timber structures may burn with flaming combustion during a fire, resulting in a relatively rapid change of the material's constitutive properties and capacity to carry internal loads. Although this can have serious implications on the structural integrity of a timber structure during and even after a fire, the design and construction of modern mass timber can take into account the behaviour of timber during and after a fire. This thesis considers the design and experimental investigation of rationalized manufacturing techniques for Glulam beams reinforced with Fibre Reinforced Polymers (FRP) that could be used in floor timber structures with improved fire and serviceability performance. In essence, introducing FRP with a relatively higher residual capacity at elevated temperatures, compared to timber, compensates for timber's loss of strength and stiffness at elevated temperatures or even when charring during a fire. This is a shift in how FRP materials are currently constrained in loadbearing applications where structural integrity must be maintained during or after a fire.

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ABSTRACT

Glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) bars are being considered as an innovative and economical alternative to stainless steel to overcome the problem of steel corrosion in concrete reinforcement. However, the concerns about the high vulnerability of GFRP bars to elevated temperature are not sufficiently well addressed in the literature, and thus FRP-reinforced concrete (RC) design codes provide little guidance, preventing their widespread use in buildings where strict fire resistance requirements have to be fulfilled. The PhD thesis aimed at contributing to fill the above-mentioned gaps in knowledge, namely by improving the knowledge about the fire behaviour of concrete members reinforced with GFRP bars, as well as proposing guidelines for fire design. To achieve these objectives, a comprehensive assessment of the topic was made by means of experimental, numerical and analytical methodologies in the following three complementary domains: (i) thermophysical and mechanical characterization of GFRP bars at elevated temperature; (ii) bond behaviour of GFRP bars in concrete at elevated temperature, and (iii) fire behaviour of GFRP-reinforced concrete slabs.

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APPLICATION TO WEB-CRIPPLING PHENOMENA**

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ABSTRACT

This thesis addresses two main research topics, both of which are applied to pultruded glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) materials and profiles: (i) fracture toughness; and (ii) web crippling of structural beams. These are considerably different topics, as fracture toughness is a topic that can be implemented in a wide variety of frameworks, whereas web-crippling is a well known and specific structural case, involving concentrated transverse loads. However, these two topics closely intersect in this thesis, as fracture toughness properties can be implemented in finite element (FE) numerical models to simulate damage evolution of brittle materials, such as GFRP composites. This numerical methodology was thus selected to simulate the web-crippling failure of pultruded GFRP profiles, a topic that currently has significant research needs. Finally, an analytical study was performed, based on the experimental and numerical results determined for web-crippling of I-section pultruded GFRP profiles. The direct strength method (DSM) was implemented in order to achieve two goals: (i) to accurately predict experimental ultimate loads; (ii) to address simultaneously the various web-crippling failure modes.

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ABSTRACT

The transition to renewable energy is helping to limit the consumption of fossil fuels and mitigate climate change. However, even low-carbon energy sources such as wind energy have environmental and social impacts, as well as benefits. A significant proportion of the overall materials embodied in a wind turbine is glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP). GFRP's attractive structural qualities has made it the material of choice for wind turbine blades for the past three decades of wind turbine technology. Wind energy deployment accelerated in the early 2000s in Europe and North America, and as the typical service life of a wind turbine is 20 years, large volumes of GFRP wind blades are now reaching end-of-life and are being decommissioned. With approximately ten metric tonnes of GFRP per installed megawatt (MW) of wind energy capacity, the global wind turbine fleet of 700 GW now embodies approximately 70,000 tonnes of GFRP blades. This volume will continue to grow very strongly in the coming decades. Prior to the completion of this thesis work, repurposing of blades had been seen as a potentially attractive solution to blade end-of-life disposal, as it sits higher on the US Environmental Protection Agency's waste hierarchy than alternative disposal methods such as landfill, incineration or co-processing waste in cement kilns. This hypothesis was the starting point for an international collaborative research project, Re-Wind (<https://www.re-wind.info/>). However there was a lack of evidence to support the hypothesis. The significance of this thesis is that it provides, for the first time, a robust methodological framework and an evidence base to support the economic, environmental and social acceptability of repurposing as a solution for end-of-life wind turbine blades.